

MESOPP

MESOPP

**3rd MESOPP Workshop
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Coonamesstt Inn
9-11 Oct 2018**

**Designing the needs for the implementation of a
global coupled acoustic-based observation-
modelling system**

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1. Foreword

MESOPP (Mesopelagic Southern Ocean Prey and Predators) is a European H2020 International Cooperation project to enhancing and focusing research and innovation cooperation with Australia. The underlying concept of MESOPP is the creation of a collaborative network and associated e-infrastructure (marine ecosystem information system) between European and Australian research teams/institutes sharing similar interests in the Southern Ocean and Antarctica, its marine ecosystem functioning and the rapid changes occurring with the climate warming and the exploitation of marine resources.

In the past 30 years, facing global knowledge issues, lacking data, addressing huge modelling challenges, we observed the successful world organisation of meteorology. These past 15 years, Europe has kick started and demonstrated similar successful structuring of the operational oceanography fostered by the Copernicus initiative (<http://marine.copernicus.eu/>), today worldwide used and recognised, fully anticipated and integrated in GOOS (Global Ocean Observing System), IOSS (Integration ocean observation system), SOOS (Southern Ocean Observing System), GODAE (the international global ocean data assimilation experiment), and IMBER (integrated marine biogeochemistry and ecosystem research).

A major R&D strategic challenge is to connect the marine ecosystem community across the fields of meteorology, climate, oceanography and biology. Lack of data, development of accurate high-end models, global coverage and need for exchange are issues that need to be overcome.

While MESOPP will focus on the enhancement of collaborations by eliminating various obstacles in establishing a common methodology and a connected network of databases of acoustic data for the estimation of micronekton biomass and validation of models, it will also contribute to a better predictive understanding of the SO based on furthering the knowledge base on key functional groups of micronekton and processes which determine ecosystem dynamics from physics to large oceanic predators. This first project and associated implementation (science network and specification of an infrastructure) should constitute the nucleus of a larger international program of acoustic monitoring and micronekton modelling to be integrated in the general framework of ocean observation following a roadmap that will be prepared during the project.

Partners

- CLS, Collecte Localisation Satellites, France
- CSIRO: Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation, Australia
- UTas: University of Tasmania, Australia
- AAD: Australian Antarctic Division, Australia
- BAS: Natural environment Research Council NERC-BAS United Kingdom
- UPMC : Université Pierre et Marie Curie France, associated to the MNHN (Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle)
- IMR: Institute of Marine Research (Havforskningsinstituttet) Norway
- UA: University of St Andrew, United Kingdom

2. Agenda and participants

The agenda and list of Participants are provided in appendix.

3. Introduction

The primary objective of MESOPP is to demonstrate the interest of establishing a common methodology and a connected network of databases of acoustic data for the estimation of micronekton biomass and validation of ocean ecosystem models. The first workshop of the project focused on the standardisation of acoustic data for micronekton modelling. The second had a special focus on the development of the database and e-infrastructure. This third meeting had the objective of progressing on the design of the needs for the implementation of a global coupled acoustic-based observation-modelling system. It was held at the Coonamesstt Inn in Falmouth, USA, 8-11 October 2018. The meeting was organized by the MESOPP coordinator P. Lehodey (CLS) with the very efficient support locally of CLS subsidiary Woodshole group (<http://www.woodsholegroup.com/>), and particularly Catherine Morey who is warmly thanked here. In addition to the MESOPP partners, the organization of the meeting in Falmouth allowed to get a strong participation from colleagues working in 10 different US academic and governmental institutions (see appendix). New Zealand was also represented with one scientist from the NIWA strongly involved in the ocean acoustic sampling program of this organisation.

MESOPP is organised around three themes: acoustic data, models and use cases. It is proposed to deliver standards for processing acoustic data to facilitate their use in ecosystem models and the estimation of biomass of mesopelagic organisms. Observations and models will help to investigate potential changes associated to climate change projections, including those on predator species of mesopelagic organisms. After a quick review of the work progress since the kick-off meeting in Sep 2016, and the planning for the 3rd year, the first day of this third workshop was devoted to a review of existing acoustic network of sampling based on opportunities and archives and to the definition of an optimal sampling strategy. The second day focused on emerging technologies in observation of mesopelagic organisms and data processing, the development of acoustic observation models and progress in ecosystem and mid-trophic level modeling. The last day was devoted to the predators of micronekton and the interest of using new mesopelagic observation and model products for better understanding in the ecology of these species. It concluded with presentation and discussions on the needs for Central Information System for acoustic data and models. The end of each meeting day was devoted to drafting the plan and ideas of the roadmap document that the project will have to deliver with the recommendations to establish a global coupled acoustic-based observation-modelling system. This report provides a summary of the meeting outcomes.

4. Project administrative and technical issues

After the opening of the MESOPP meeting by Patrick Lehodey, the agenda was adopted with minor modifications on the schedule and P. Lehodey presented a review on the project organization.

4.1. Project deliverables

The deliverable D4.3 was delivered in time thanks to the recent recruitment of post-doctoral researcher Haris Kunnath by CSIRO. Conversely, with the ending post-doctoral contract of A. Conchon at UPMC, the deliverable D4.8 is late. Its completion is taken in charge by the project coordinator. It was stressed that the deliverable date of the roadmap document D2.7 (end of Nov) is very short, especially since another report (D4.4) is also due at the same date. Some delays are expected for both,

while the report of the workshop should be delivered earlier than planned. The deliverable D4.5 will benefit of the recent recruitment of Joe Potts at AAD. She already made a visit in CLS to learn about the SEAPODYM micronekton model. Other remaining deliverables should be submitted in due time without any expected problem.

Status at the date of report writing: 4 Jan 2019

	Title	Lead Beneficiary	Status	Due Date
D1.1	Project Management plan	CLS	Approved	
D1.2	Quarterly project progress report including technical and finance period report	CLS	Approved	
D1.4	Dissemination & exploitation plan	CLS	Approved	
D1.5	Dissemination through web site and social networks	CLS	Approved	
D2.1	Report on Workshop 1	CSIRO	Approved	
D2.2	Report on Workshop 2	CLS	Approved	
D2.4	First release of web site	CLS	Approved	
D2.5	Release of web site with e-infrastructure (catalogue and data access services	CLS	Approved	
D3.1	Report on acoustic processing routine and quality checking methods	BAS	Approved	
D3.2	Reference dataset of 38 kHz acoustic backscatter for South Atlantic sector Southern Ocean	BAS	Approved	
D3.3	Reference dataset of 38 kHz acoustic backscatter for South Indian ocean sector	UPMC	Approved	
D3.4	Reference dataset of 38 kHz acoustic backscatter for South Pacific Ocean sector	CSIRO	Approved	
D3.5	Collocated NASC and oceanographic variables	UPMC	Approved	
D3.6	Definition of taxonomic/functional group in MESOPP models in relation to existing acoustic information	CSIRO	Approved	
D4.1	documentation of the models, standardisation and protocols to be used for model inter-comparisons	UTAS	Approved	
D4.2	Acoustic observation model linking ecological models to acoustic signals	IMR	Approved	
D4.3	Methods to process acoustic data from vessels of opportunity for use in ecosystem model validation	CSIRO	Approved	
D4.6	Atlas of the main mesopelagic fish in the Southern Ocean	UPMC	Approved	
D4.7	Modelisation of potential habitats of the main mesopelagic fish according to environmental parameters	USTAN	Approved	
D4.8	Characterizing large scale micronekton assemblages	UPMC/CLS	submitted	
D4.9	Use of micronekton data and models to improve ecology of top predators	USTAN	submitted	
D1.3	Final report	CLS	Active	31/05/2019
D1.6	Dissemination Report	CLS	Active	31/05/2019
D2.3	Report on Workshop 3	CLS	Active	31/05/2019
D2.6	Final release with update of products	CLS	Active	31/03/2019
D2.7	Roadmap towards a global integrated observing and modelling system	CLS	Pending	30/11/2018
D3.7	Update on definition of taxonomic/functional group in MESOPP models in relation to new technology	CSIRO	Active	28/02/2019
D4.4	statistical methods for estimating skill of mesopelagic models to replicate acoustic observations	CLS	Pending	30/11/2018
D4.5	Report on model inter-comparison, including publication of the methods used in this project	UTAS	Active	31/05/2019
D4.10	Joint Australian and French reports to CCAMLR	AAD	Active	31/05/2019

4.2. Postdocs / short-term contracts

- Roland Proud is still based in UA but is now funded on CSIRO MESOPP budget.
- Anna Conchon finished her contract in UPMC end of April 2018.
- Alejandro Ariza finished his contract in BAS.
- Joe Potts has been recruited by AAD on a short-term contract.
- Haris Kunnath has been recruited by CSIRO on a short-term contract.
- A master student internship (Claire Godet) has been funded in 2018 by Sorbonne Univ.

4.3. Final report

The project will finish at the end of June 2019. All deliverables need to be submitted by this date, and then approved by the EC. Several of them are due end of May. As for the interim report, the final report of the project includes a technical and financial part. Further information will be provided to all partners.

4.4. Communication

Since last meeting in June 2017, another series of newsletters have been published on the MESOPP web site (Table 1). We need more to come! MESOPP activities have been included in various presentations in international conferences. Nice photos published on the MESOPP facebook account, and the (Small) Monster of the ocean gallery encounters some success!

Table 1: List of news published on MESOPP web site

Date	Who	Title
Aug 2018	Vinca/Patrick	Elephant seals Predators & prey use case
Jul. 2018	Vinca/Patrick	Albatrosses predators & prey use case
Apr. 2018	Roland	Estimating micronekton biomass
Feb. 2018	Vinca	Southern Ocean marine animals in the headlines
Feb. 2018	Cédric	MOBYDICK
Feb. 2018	Sophie	MESOPP on a Cruise -2018
Dec. 2017	Roland	How to use acoustic data in ecosystem models
Dec. 2017	Vinca	Model and acoustic data now available on MESOPP web site!
Nov. 2017	Vinca	MEASO 2018 Abstract reminder! Due 30th November
Nov. 2017	Nils-Olav	Sampling mesopelagic fish from trawl surveys using the Deep Vision in-trawl camera system
Oct 2017	Cédric	Tracking ecological hotspots in the Southern Ocean
Oct 2017	Lauriane	Major changes on the Antarctic fur seal breeding success predicted by coupled models
Jul 2017	Patrick	2nd MESOPP Workshop at Univ of St Andrews
May 2017	Rudy	Investigation of deep-scattering layers with a profiling lagrangian acoustic optical system
May 2017	Rowan	Multispecies size spectra models for East Antarctica
Mar. 2017	Patrick	Complementarities of GREENUP and MESOPP projects
Mar. 2017	Beth/Jess	Atlantis ecosystem model for East Antarctica
Feb. 2017	Roland	MESOPP in the Antarctic Circumpolar Expedition
Jan. 2017	Anna	THEMISTO campaign aboard the Marion Dufresne
Jan. 2017	Sophie	MESOPP on a cruise
Dec. 2016	Andrew C.	Creation of the largest marine natural reserve, close to Antarctica
Oct. 2016	Anna	SEAPODYM-MTL, modeling the ocean micronekton biomass
Sep. 2016	Patrick	MESOPP project officially started in Hobart

5. Progress in standardisation of acoustic processing

Sophie Fielding (BAS) presented a summary of the report (Deliverable D3.1) on acoustic processing routine and quality checking methods. The report summarises the post-processing steps used to generate calibrated, post-processed S_v freely-available from the MESOPP website (www.mesopp.eu) and include the NetCDF format proposed that is compliant with ICES (version 1.10) metadata convention.

Datasets from 6 ships covering three sectors of the Southern Ocean are available. Data were collected from research vessels during research cruises and logistical transits and from fishing vessels during logistical transits. In each case standardised data collection settings (Ryan 2011) were required in order for the data to be considered comparable and available for inclusion in a larger observing network. The echosounders were calibrated and then post-processed following similar steps, but with different software or settings. Many parts of the post-processing are now undertaken with semi-automated filters, only requiring a user to provide parameterisation of the filters depending on sampling platform and weather conditions. Remaining steps to enable full automated processing is identification of “false bottom” in the acoustic data and automated parameterisation of the filters.

A preliminary comparison indicated that two of the three post-processing methods used generated similar values of water column NASC integrated from 0 to 800 m. There were some differences between biases with depth, although all still low. To ensure good data quality and assurance processes, data processing techniques should be compared on common data sets. Metrics of data quality can be produced, especially for the background noise and the range detection limit.

Interestingly, the impact of data processing methods on data assimilation in SEAPODYM-MTL has been tested by Anna and shown generally a very good correlation between the values of energy transfer efficiency coefficient estimated either with BAS or CSIRO processing methods. There are occasional large differences for the coefficient associated to the epipelagic functional group. Open-source software are needed to read, process and visualise the data (e.g. pyecholab, echopy, ESP3, matecho, Pyechomask). It was highlighted in the discussion that though it is difficult to apply the same process to all data, it is not an issue as long as the process is detailed in the NetCDF. Routine for intercomparison / intercalibration of data should be developed as in the GEOTRACES programme.

Haris Kunnath and Rudy Kloser have just recently provided a review on vessels of opportunity bioacoustic methods (D4.3)¹. They are useful for cost-effective mapping of mesopelagic communities at regional and global scale, but the conversion of acoustic data (Sv) to biomass is still a problem in absence of ground-truthing with respect to species composition. When interpreting the acoustic data it is important to understand the corrections applied (detailed in the report) for vessel calibration, transducer motion correction, sound speed and absorption variation. The motion and sound speed and absorption corrections have been shown to be range dependant that can greatly influence the lower mesopelagic (400–800 m depth) derived metrics by >50%. In order to mitigate bias in interpretation and to facilitate large-scale uptake of bioacoustic data in ecosystem models, it is recommended that:

- The echosounder should be calibrated routinely to establish traceable calibration history and continued expected performance for each vessel.
- The data processing methods (including user-defined filter parameters) need to be well specified and tested with reference data sets to standardize between data providers.
- The naming conventions and metadata content of the processed data should be consistently followed to generate a globally consistent bioacoustic database.

6. Extension of the acoustic network of sampling

A series of presentations allowed then to review the existing archives and ongoing sampling programmes of acoustic data that could be opportunistically used to extend the observation network at global scale.

¹ http://www.mesopp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/D4.3_MESOPP-18-0009-Acoustic-data-from-vessels-of-opportunity.pdf

The New Zealand acoustic monitoring programme (in the Southern Ocean) was presented by Pablo Escobar-Flores (NIWA). The objectives are to characterise the distribution and abundance of the MTL organisms in the New Zealand sector of the Southern Ocean (SO), to produce explanatory and predictive models of acoustic backscatter to lessen lack of observations and to provide estimates of biological density from bulk acoustic backscatter for the region.

Opportunistic raw acoustic data have been collected since 2008 from toothfish fishing vessels during their transit between NZ and Antarctica (Figure 1, Table 2). Data are processed according to the IMOS protocols and compiled into NetCDF files (Sv at 10 m x 1 km vertical x horizontal resolution). However, an additional grooming filtering process is applied that may result in difference of 10-20% compared to IMOS method. Research cruise onboard the RV Tangaroa allowed to characterize the same region with net sampling and in situ profiles. One striking result from these comparative analyses is that the mean backscatter is lower in the central region than in the northern region despite higher biomass of mesopelagic fish estimated from net sampling (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Total number of acoustic transect (n =28) between New Zealand and Antarctica.

Vessel name	Nº of transects	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	Size (Gb)
San Aotea II	11	1		2	2	2	2	2	39.7
San Aspiring	5			1	2	1	1		16.1
Janas	6			1	2		1	2	21.39
Tangaroa	6	2		2			2		92.8

Table 2: Details of acoustic transects in the NIWA archive.

	Mean backscatter (Sa)	Mean mesopelagic fish density (g m ⁻²)
Northern	2.2E-05	20.5
Central	1.3E-05	39.3
Southern	8.5E-07	6.4

Figure 2: Comparison of backscatter signal and biomass estimates from net trawl sampling in the SO sector of New Zealand (From P. Escobar-Flores et al 2018).

The US Antarctic Marine Living Resource Programme is also conducting mesopelagic fish research in the Antarctic Peninsula using nets sampling, acoustics and predator diets. This research was presented by Christian Reiss (NOAA, SWFSC). The study area is relatively small but dynamic and complex, and changing very rapidly. The area is also an important area for oceanic predators, i.e., seals, whales and seabirds. Net sampling indicate that the mesopelagic fish community is dominated by two genus (*Electrona* and *Gymnoscopelus*) with essentially two species for each (*E. antarctica* and *E. carlsbergi*; *G. braueri* and *G. nicholsi*). Three frequencies (38, 120 and 200 kHz) are used to allocate backscatter

to krill and mesopelagics. In summer, krill is observed in the upper 150m during day and moving into the upper 30 to 50 meters at night. In contrast, mesopelagic fish NASC is concentrated at approximately 200m during the day and occupies the entire range between 200m and the surface at night. There are substantial differences in spatial distributions across the Antarctic Peninsula (Figure 3). Krill nasc is found throughout the sample area. In contrast, mesopelagic fish NASC is concentrated in the zone between the boundary and the Antarctic Circumpolar Current Front (ACCF). In general, the patterns of fish NASC align closely with the distribution of *Electrona* from the net tows. There is considerable interannual variability in abundance (NASC) over the time series (Figure 3) and also long term change observed in the mean age of *G. nicholsi* (Figure 4). Historical U. S. AMLR data are available for collaboration (some data at NCEI and metadata provided to SONA). Future data collection will be limited while an automatized monitoring system is progressively implemented.

Figure 3: Results from the US Antarctic Marine Living Resource Program (kindly from C. Reiss).

Change in spatial and temporal abundance of krill (black continuous line) and mesopelagic fish (dotted line) is monitored through acoustic backscatter deduced from 3 acoustic frequencies.

Figure 4: Results from the US Antarctic Marine Living Resource Program showing a declining mean age in the mesopelagic fish *G. nicholsi* (kindly from C. Reiss).

David Demer from the NOAA Southwest Fisheries Science Center presented past and ongoing work regarding the monitoring of the deep scattering layer in the California Current Ecosystem (CCE), that

includes acoustic and trawl sampling collected during annual (CCE surveys) and seasonal (CALCOFI) surveys. The surveys use multi-frequency echosounders, autonomous platforms (e.g., saildrone) and continuous records (moorings). Wideband sampling of plankton and micronekton are validated using plankton and opening-closing nets, and cameras.

Figure 5: Sampling program in the California Current Ecosystem and example of continuous acoustic recording from a mooring. (Kindly from D. Demer)

NOAA is also very active in the Atlantic Ocean for sampling the meso/bathypelagic communities. These activities were presented by Michael Jech from the NOAA North-East Fisheries Science Center. In the Gulf of Mexico, the DEPEND consortium has been established after the 2010 Deepwater Horizon oil spill. The project (PI: Tracey Sutton) is multidisciplinary and includes various type of data presented on the consortium website (cf <http://dependconsortium.org/>). The NEFSC collaborates with the Norwegian Institute of Marine Research with several projects doing acoustics and trawls sampling in the north Atlantic (Irminger Sea), Indian Ocean (Arabia Sea, Gulf of Oman), and Benguela. HARMES (Harvesting the mesopelagics – ecological and management implications) is a project funded (2018-2020) by the Norwegian Research Council (PI: Webjørn Melle, IMR). A EU proposal has been submitted by IMR colleagues (MEESO) that focus specifically on the mesopelagics. The NEFSC collaborate with Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI) in a new large project (DEEP-SEE) just starting and presented later by Andone Lavery (PI). It is noted that the NOAA ship *Okeanos Explorer* dedicated to ocean exploration has now moved to the North Atlantic. It will be likely involved in research surveys of the ASPIRE (Atlantic Seafloor Partnership for Integrated Research and Exploration) project that will very likely include mesopelagic sampling with multi-frequencies and wideband echo sounder. A large research effort is also devoted to protected species (marine mammals, seabirds and turtles) with the project AMAPPS (Atlantic Marine Assessment Program for Protected Species), an inter-agency program involving NOAA, Bureau of Ocean Energy and Management (BOEM), US Fish and Wildlife, and US Navy. Echosounder data were collected to address interest in distribution of prey – i.e., the deep-scattering layer and meso/bathypelagic communities. This also include passive acoustic and visual

sightings. Associated to this program, Erin LaBrecque is doing a PhD study (Duke University) on the variability in Acoustic Scattering Across the Shelf Break (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Examples of transect along the shelf break with acoustic characterization (kindly from E. LaBrecque).

Among other potential useful sources of acoustic and mesopelagic biomass estimates, there are the project IDEADOS in the Mediterranean Sea around the Balearic Islands (contact Maria Peña at Spanish Institute of Oceanography, Mallorca, Spain) and the regular transects collected during maintenance cruises of the PIRATA moorings in the equatorial Atlantic (contact: Bernard Bourles, Jeremy Habasque and Arnaud Bertrand, IRD FR). In the tropical Pacific Ocean, the research program BIOPELAGOS in collaboration between IRD Noumea (PI: Christophe Menkès) and the Secretariat of the Pacific Community (PI: Valérie Allain) is investigating vertical distribution variability and environmental associations of pelagic fauna from acoustic and multiple physical, chemical and biological variables (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Acquisition of acoustic data in the Equatorial Atlantic (PIRATA) and tropical Pacific (BIOPELAGOS) (Kindly from A. Bertrand, Jérémie Habasque and Christophe Menkès)

Examples of infrastructures to archive and diffuse large volume of acoustic data have been presented with the NOAA National Centers for Environmental Information by C. Anderson (Project Leader: Carrie Wall) and Nils-Olav Handegard from IMR (Norway). The database contains both active and passive acoustic data. Active acoustic represents ~72TB from 12 systems, 30 vessels and for the period 1998-2018 (Figure 8); ~20% collected from EK60 and 30% from EK80. Metadata are stored in an ORACLE

database and the raw instrument files are stored in a tape-based archive system. The geoportal allows any user to discover, query, and request the archived (raw) data.

A user can then select a region of interest or use the filter tool to identify a specific time period, source, vessel, instrument or frequency desired to further narrow down their search through the archived data. When a cruise is selected on the map viewer, the cruise's attributes are displayed showing data citation and links to associated datasets. A digital object identifier is created for all NOAA and academic cruises. These permanent citations are visible on the map viewer and most importantly credit the data provider. This is the citation that should be used if the data are used. Links to associated ancillary data (like cruise reports and calibration data) are available along with a netCDF of the processed CTD data from the World Ocean Database. Currently open-source python-based data processing tools are developed to increase efficiency in NCEI image processing routine and promote broader research and collaboration within community.

Figure 8. Cruise tracks of acoustic data archived at www.ngdc.noaa.gov/maps/water_column_sonar with example of metadata for one track.

On the European side, the acoustic archive is centralized by ICES, but with the primary objective of estimating biomass of key exploited fish stocks. There is no specific data processing for mesopelagic species and the raw acoustic data are not available through this web site. It is recommended that in the processing of acoustic signal, extracted energy associated to a given species or "class" be identified by standardised masks, with the sum of classes equate the total energy. One or several classes could be mesopelagic species or functional groups representing acoustic Earth observation Variables (EoV). It is also recommended to store the .raw files.

7. Optimal sampling strategy for global biomass estimate

Given the massive volume of data that a global coverage with acoustic multi-frequencies would represent it becomes necessary to identify the priorities and the most useful datasets to (re)process. The first extrapolations of limited datasets to global biomass estimates of mesopelagic fish provide a large range of uncertainty, roughly between 1 and 20 Gt of biomass (Table 3). Roland Proud presented a revision of his first attempt of estimating global biomass of fish biomass (Proud et al 2018). He estimated uncertainty in biomass by running multiple simulations over his model parameter distributions and considering three scenarios of species composition:

- S1- All fish with gas bladders;

S2- the smallest length classes always had gas bladders and the proportion of fish that lost their bladders as they grew increased following a cosine curve.

S3- a large proportion of small (young) and large (old) fish were without gas bladders and the proportion with gas bladders increased toward the centre of the length distribution.

The new estimate range between 1.8 (lower quartile of S1) and 16.0 Gt (upper quartile of S3). If the scenario S2 can be considered the most likely, acoustic derived estimate could be reduced to between 2.1 and 8.9 Gt (lower quartile to upper quartile).

For comparison, the global biomass predicted for all functional groups of the SEAPODYM MTL model is in the range of 1.7 Gt with its current parameterization (Figure 9). This estimate is sensitive to the few parameters of the model. First the conversion coefficient between g carbon and g wet weight. Here a value of 7.92 is used (Lehodey et al 2010) while for instance Anderson et al. (2018) use 11.9. Thus, with this latter coefficient SEAPODYM estimate would be increased by 50%, i.e. just above Anderson et al. estimate. Then the energy transfer efficiency coefficient is set to 12.5 % but there are studies suggesting higher values especially in upwelling systems. Therefore, this estimate is certainly in its lower range. A method is developed to run optimal sampling simulation experiments (OSSE) with SEAPODYM to investigate if there are ecological regions more favorable than other to estimate the model parameters.

Table 3: Estimates of global (open-ocean) mesopelagic fish biomass

Estimate	Reference	Method
1 Gt	Gjoseter and Kawaguchi (1980)	Ocean trawl data
14.3 to 19.5 Gt	Irigoien et al. (2014)	Acoustics
< 1.4 Gt	Jennings and Collingridge (2015)	Macroecological model
2.4 Gt	Anderson et al. (2018)	Food-web model
1.8 to 16.0 Gt	Proud et al (2018)	Acoustics

Figure 9. Example of biomass distribution predicted for one (resident lower mesopelagic) of the four mesopelagic functional groups of SEAPODYM (with parameterization of Lehodey et al 2010).

8. Emerging technologies in observation and data processing

The traditional but still essential trawl sampling method provides key information on the species composition of mesopelagic communities. A strong effort has been devoted to the production of an

Atlas of Mesopelagic fish species for the Southern Ocean that has been recently updated with new collected observations (Deliverable D4.6) and presented by Cedric Cotté (Sorbonne Univ; MNHN). Clustering analyses are used to identify relationships between these species communities and the oceanographic conditions. Currently five groups of myctophid communities are identified, but with weak species dominance. Boundaries between these groups are associated to temperature of 5 and 12 °C and the species richness is higher in subtropics.

Genomics provide new technologies that are rapidly developing and should help to improve at low cost our knowledge of species assemblages in the different eco-regions of the ocean. Hilary G. Morrison (Marine Biological Laboratory, Univ Chicago, USA) presented a review of these techniques that have been already largely used in the study of microbial food web. A promising technique is the sampling of environmental DNA (eDNA) released by organisms in the water in the form of skin cells, scales and excretion to be sequenced (barcoding) and then compared to existing databases. If the species is not yet in these catalogues, it is possible at least to characterize the composition by larger taxa. The iBOL initiative (<http://www.ibol.org/>) is developing a barcode reference library (BOLD) that includes a hand-held device to provide real-time access to identifications by anyone in any setting. One example of application is provided in Stoeckle et al (2017), with eDNA used to detect seasonal fish abundance and habitat preference.

The other major technological progress for the observation of the mesopelagic ecosystem is the wideband echosounder, that should help to identify the main group of species. The Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI) has designed a dedicated instrument (Figure 10) that includes this wide band technology and two optical high-resolution imagery systems. The LAPIS (Large Area Plankton Imaging System) and the holographic camera. Preliminary results from the first cruise were presented by Andone Lavery (WHOI, USA). The imagery systems provide incredible high-resolution picture of zooplankton species and jellies. One challenge is now to process the terabytes of data that are generated by this instrument. Biomass at depths beyond the DSL observed with shipboard systems is significantly higher than previously thought.

Figure 10. The "Deep-See": A Towed Vehicle for Quantification of the Twilight Zone

Autonomous vehicles for observation at sea are quickly developing. Rudy Kloser (CSIRO, Aus) shown the first results achieved with the use of Sairdrone for acoustic sampling (Figure 11). A 38/200 kHz combo transducer is installed with many other sensors for atmospheric and ocean parameters. The drone is equipped with surface cameras and AIS. It can be deployed for several months up to 1 year.

The first try at sea indicated a very good stability of the drone allowing to record high quality acoustic transects.

Figure 11. The saildrone developed together between Australia CSIRO and NOAA-PMEL has multiple atmospheric and oceanic sensors and acoustic transducers to collect 38 and 200 kHz data.

Another interesting future source of acoustic data for the SO could come from the POLARPOD initiative led by the French explorer Jean-Louis Etienne. Patrick Lehodey gave a brief view of the project. The building phase should start in 2019 and the test phase are planned in 2021 before a research cruise in the Southern Ocean in 2022 (<https://www.oceanpolaire.org/en/polar-pod/>). Two wideband echosounders EK80 looking upward and downward should be installed in the structure.

All these emerging technologies generate high volume of data that require to progress in the development of acoustic data processing. One example of automatic processing was given by Sophie Fielding (BAS, UK). She presented a software development (Rapidkrill) to process acoustic data onboard Antarctic krill fishing vessels (Figure 12). The objective is to propose this open-source software toolbox to undertake unsupervised automated processing of acoustic data to krill density estimates. An onboard Vessel Data processing and analysis System (VDS) connects up the processing toolbox with current day satellite communications to deliver “real-time” estimates of Antarctic krill (Figure 13). The data processing generates also metrics of data quality to inform vessels when surveying conditions are suitable in real-time. The software is currently installed onboard the RV RRS James Clark Ross for testing and validation phase.

Figure 12: Chain of automatic processing for the “Rapidkrill” software.

Figure 13: Conceptual scheme of the “Rapidkrill” opensource software.

9. Progress in observation models: from acoustic to biomass

The progress in the development of acoustic observation models was presented by Roland Proud (UA/UK). This work was reported in the deliverable D4.2: Acoustic observation model: linking ecological models to acoustic signals, submitted in July. If eco-regions with homogeneous species community can be identified, there is still a need to convert the acoustic signal in biomass in these regions. This should be done by linking acoustic observation models to ecosystem models that can provide the information needed to convert model-predicted-abundance into echo intensity. The method proposed includes following steps:

1. Identify the key model components and available acoustic data (and frequencies) by eco-regions.
2. Identify species and proportion of organisms producing most of the backscattering intensity (considering frequency range).
3. Determine which target strength models (and therefore which parameters) are required to convert ecosystem model predictions (e.g., a species or a group of species) into backscattering intensity.
4. Include required TS model parameters in ecosystem model state, with dependence to (mean) depth and size of organisms.
5. Obtain other parameters from other sources e.g. net-haul data.

However, the problem of siphonophore still must be solved since these organisms contribute largely to the total acoustic signal. While this group should be separately simulated in ecosystem models, it is also needed to better discriminate the signal associated to siphonophore by using multiple frequencies. This is the focus of the deliverable D3.7 “Potential update on the definition of taxonomic/functional/energetic group in MESOPP models in relation to new acoustic technology information”. Rudy Kloser (CSIRO, AUS) provided a summary of this ongoing work. The combination of optical systems with multiple acoustic frequencies on a Lagrangian profiler provides extremely useful comparison between the acoustic detection and the abundance detected by counting individual organisms using the optical system (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Abundance of organisms by large taxa counted from the optical system and associated acoustic signal along the vertical profile during a research cruise with the CSIRO Profiling Lagrangian Acoustic Optical System (PLAOS).

To conclude this session, Nils-Olav Handegard (IMR, NOR) presented the ongoing work in IMR to develop the Pelagic Fish Simulator Tool (PELFOSS). Specific acoustic observation models are designed for target exploited species as the mackerel, herring and blue whiting. Winter and summer sampling cruises are regularly conducted to estimate the species biomass. The acoustic data collected could be used for mesopelagic and other species groups. This requires proposing a data format (NetCDF) that keeps track of the backscatter data identified and used for each species/group of species through the use of masks. Further progress concerning the acoustic modelling of mesopelagic fish are expected with the EU MEESO research project. In that case new acoustic models for these mesopelagic species would be added to PELFOSS.

10. Progress in ecosystem / mid-trophic modelling

Several ecosystem models are used and developed in MESOPP. Patrick Lehodey (CLS, FR) summarized the recent progress for SEAPODYM, concerning the Low and Mid-Trophic Level (LMTL) components. This LMTL product has been included in the European Copernicus catalogue of product. The first global reanalysis will be delivered early 2019. It will be global at resolution $0.25^\circ \times$ week. Special research efforts are focused on the problem of high latitudes, e.g. Southern Ocean, where no ocean color data are available in winter. The other axes of research include better representation of shallow water domains, and potentially further functional groups, e.g., to match the acoustic observations. The global reanalysis will be updated regularly to approach realtime with a few months of time lag and to integrate progress and new developments. Optimization of parameter estimates remains a major issue for evaluation and validation (A. Conchon, M-O, FR). The maximum likelihood estimation approach used with the model should benefit of the progress in acoustic observation models (above) that could be integrated directly in the ecosystem model optimisation method. A study investigated optimal system sampling experiments (OSSEs) for estimating model parameters from biomass observations. It suggests that eco-regions with warm waters and intermediate to low dynamics would be a better choice rather than the cold regions, especially if they are also strongly dynamics. Therefore, extension of the sampling network to temperate and tropical regions would be also beneficial to the biomass estimate in the Southern Ocean with this model.

The ecosystem modelling effort by Australian partners include a size-based approach, Ecopath and Atlantis. They were presented by Andrew Constable (AAD, AUS). Ecopath is developed for 4 different quadrants of the Southern Ocean. The model provides a mass-balanced snapshot of the foodweb (e.g.,

Figure 15) based on the dietary data contained in the SCAR Southern Ocean Diet and Energetics Database.

Figure 15: Simplified food pathway in the Southern Ocean (From Constable et al 2017).

A size-based model for the Kerguelen Axis region is developed that includes various groups of zooplankton, micronektonic fishes and squids, and micronekton predators. The Atlantis model is driven by physical outputs from a regional (ROMS) circulation model and sea ice satellite data. It has 43 functional groups or species with fish seabirds and mammals discretized in several cohorts (Table 4). These last two models are still in their phase of parameterization.

Table 4: Definition of functional groups and species in Atlantis for the Antarctica-Kerguelen axis

Kerguelen Axis ATLANTIS model	GroupType	Name	Number of Cohorts	Details Group Type
	Functional groups and species:		Krill	6
Fish		Fish_Pelagic	10	FISH
		Fish_Mesopelagic	4	
		Toothfish	20	
		Icefish	6	
Cephalopods		Cephalopods	1	CEP
Mammal--seals		Antarctic_Fur_Seal	10	MAMMAL
		Elephant_Seal	10	
		Crabeater_Seal	10	
		Leopard_Seal	15	
Bird		Other_Seal	10	BIRD
		Adelie_Penguin	15	
		Emperor_Penguin	10	
		Other_Penguins	10	
		Albatross	20	
Mammal--whales		Skuas	15	MAMMAL
		Other_Seabirds	12	
		Minke_Whales	15	
		Other_Baleen_Whales	20	
		Orca-A	20	
	Orca-B	20		
	Orca-C	20		
	Sperm_Whales	25		

11. Mesopelagic prey and predators

Roland Proud (UA, UK) shown preliminary results on his ongoing study to investigate the link between dive behaviour of elephant seals from the Kerguelen region and the observations of deep scattering layers from acoustic transects. He has proposed a method to extract the depth boundaries of the scattering layers observed at frequencies ≤ 38 kHz, and then search for statistical relationships between these depths and the intensity of signal with the changes in seal dive behaviour. Similar approach could be used for other predators (e.g. seabird and whale observations). Alice Della Penna (Marie Skłodowska-Curie Fellow, Univ. Washington, USA and UBO, FR) is doing a postdoc research on the mesoscale variability of zooplankton and micronekton in the North Atlantic. In cooperation with the NAAMES project (the North Atlantic Aerosols and Marine Ecosystems Study), large datasets of observation are made available from 4 research cruises (2015-18) in the North Atlantic. They include physical variables, phytoplankton and bio-optics and acoustic (several frequencies) allowing to characterize 7 cyclonic and 7 anticyclonic eddies as well as several locations outside mesoscale eddies. Acoustic backscattering is particularly intense in the mesopelagic layer in anticyclonic eddies (Figure 16), and is positively correlated with Sea Level Anomaly (positive in anticyclones) as also observed seasonally by Fennell & Rose (2015). There is no or even anti-correlation between primary production and acoustic backscattering at depth. The possibly higher concentration of mesopelagic prey in anticyclonic eddies could be related to the feeding behaviour of white sharks tracked in the North Atlantic (Gaubert et al 2018).

Figure 16: Top-left panel: Positions of anticyclonic (red) and cyclonic (blue) eddies and mode water (yellow) observed during the NAAMES research cruises. Bottom and right panels: examples of surface chlorophyll concentration and acoustic backscattering of an anticyclone (red, S1), a cyclone (blue, S2) and a mode-water eddy (yellow, S3).

The interest of using micronekton biomass distribution predicted by SEAPODYM was tested by Jason Roberts (Duke Univ., USA) to model the habitats and distributions of deep-diving marine mammals in the North-East Atlantic. These outputs are then feeding the US Navy Marine Species Density Database used by the Navy Acoustic Effects Model (NAEMO). Every 5 years, the U.S. Navy must estimate the number of individuals of each marine mammal “stock” that will be “taken” during testing and training activities, and seek a permit. This is to prohibits injury or disturbance of marine mammals in U.S. waters or by U.S. citizens on the high seas (worldwide), as required by the US Marine Mammal Protection Act. Density maps are produced by statistical models using physical variables, typically SST,

kinetic energy, currents, surface chlorophyll, and bathymetry, distance to the coast, ... The study tested the introduction of biomass functional groups micronekton as new explanatory variables. For 4 of 5 deep-divers groups or species tested (beaked whales, sperm whale, dwarf and pygmy sperm whales, pilot whales, and striped dolphin) SEAPODYM micronekton biomass covariates yielded better fitting density models than lower-trophic covariates (chlorophyll, NPP). Consistently, models for deeper divers selected deeper SEAPODYM layers (Figure 17). This first analysis was done using climatologies and should be revised using contemporaneous covariate values and new upgraded micronekton products.

Biological covariate	REML	% Dev. Expl.
Lower mesopelagic layer, day	2885.5	37.4
Lower mesopelagic layer, night	2886.9	37.3
None*	2893.3	36.4

*All others were not significant and dropped from the model

Figure 17: Best slope and abyss model for the sperm whale (June-September only) and resulting density map.

SEAPODYM micronekton is also used to model the spatial population dynamics of the Atlantic bluefin tuna. Molly Lutcavage (LPRC, USA) introduced the research and management issues for this species intensively exploited for many decades. Ecology, movements and behaviour of this bluefin has been studied with electronic tags. Two eastern and western stocks are considered by the international management organisation (ICCAT) supposed to spawning uniquely in the Gulf of Mexico and the Mediterranean Sea respectively. They are not supposed to mix in their spawning grounds while tagging data have demonstrated that they use the same feeding grounds in the North Atlantic (Figure 18). Recent observations, however, suggest that other spawning sites are possible, especially the slope sea, east of the US coast. The understanding of these spatial dynamics with spawning and feeding migration are key questions for a better management. They are investigated with the fish population dynamics module of SEAPODYM relying on the micronekton functional groups for the definition of feeding and spawning habitats. P. Lehodey presented the preliminary results. A statistical approach is used to estimate the habitat and movement model parameters with a likelihood function built on tagging data pseudo-observations. The model can predict the spawning migration in the Gulf of Mexico with a good timing. Spawning is also predicted outside of the Gulf. Results are sensitive to the resolution of the model. The physical forcing at ¼ degree resolution seems to be insufficient for a good representation of the dynamics in the Strait of Florida region characterised by a complex bathymetry.

The last presentation for this session was by Cédric Cotté (MNHN, Univ. Sorbonne, Fr) who is investigating the physical mechanisms driving pelagic trophic niches of top predators in the Kerguelen region. The Kerguelen region is characterized by a rich ecosystem with a plume of high chlorophyll source leeward of the island and enriched by sources of iron, which is often a limiting factor of the photosynthesis in the deep ocean. The age of iron-enriched waters is linked to length in food chain: Below 60 days bloom waters are dominated by crustacean (grazers); above 60 days the water mass

support mainly fish (mid-trophic). The 2°C isotherm seems to be a thermal barrier for many (stenothermic) fish.

Figure 18: Atlantic bluefin tuna case study.

- Top: dispersals based on 375 total tags (299 > 185cm) for the year 2016.
- Bottom left: Simulated released tagged fish
- Bottom right: Simulated position of tagged fish in May.

12. Central Information System for acoustic data and models

The last session of the workshop was devoted to a presentation by Vardis Tsontos (NASA, JPL, USA) on the Oceanographic Data Access Services & Initiatives in USA followed by a discussion on the future and extension of a MESOPP-type CIS.

USA have implemented a series of Distributed Active Archive Centers (DAACs) with discipline-oriented databases. The example of the Physical Oceanography center was described in more details (PO.DAAC). It provides several physical variables derived from satellite observations with different levels (L0 -> L4) from raw data to gridded interpolated product. It is planned to move to a Cloud infrastructure, especially because the SWOT mission will exponentially increase the amount of data to store. The access to data through anonymous ftp will be closed in June 2019. The web service APIs for data access uses the standard OPeNDAP remote data access protocol for serving georeferenced data over the Internet and THREDDS Data Servers (TDS) that provides metadata and data access for scientific datasets. THREDDS Dataset Inventory Catalogues are used to provide virtual directories of available data and their associated metadata. These catalogues can be generated dynamically or statically. For visualization of data, the Live Access Server (LAS) is a highly configurable Web server designed to provide flexible access to geo-referenced 4-dimensional scientific data. It can present distributed data sets as a unified virtual data base using OPeNDAP networking. The LAS allows a user to visualize data with on-the-fly graphics, request custom subsets of variables in 1-, 2-, 3- or 4-dimensions and in a choice of file formats and compare variables from distributed locations.

Vardis also presented the Oceanographic *In-situ* data Interoperability Project (OIIP: <https://oiip.jpl.nasa.gov>), a two-year project funded by NASA's Advancing Collaborative Connections for Earth System Science (ACCESS) Program. The objective is to improve technologies for the

integration of oceanographic *in-situ* and satellite datasets representing multivariate datasets from diverse observational platforms. The characteristics of this new web interface tool are:

- Integrated visualization of raster and vector-based *in situ* & satellite datasets
- Synchronized horizontal and vertical views of data and their evolution over time
- Accurate temporal representation of data & time interval control
- Integrated Data Search & Filtering capability
- Performant, high data volume throughput (data decimation algorithm)
- Elegant and intuitive browser-based user interface
- Open Source technology components (JPL-CMC, GeoServer, Solr, postgresSQL)

One selected case study concerned conventional field campaign and marine animal electronic tagging data (<https://youtu.be/CgOTwWWMhdc>).

A generalized web-based conversion tool called ROSETTA has been also improved to offer easy way to produce standards compliant netCDF data files with CF/ACDD metadata from generic, columnar ASCII data file inputs. The OIIP project encourages further active community development of this software. Code developed under the OIIP project is available Open Source via the links below to their respective repositories on Github:

OIIP Data Viewer: <https://github.com/oiip/oiip-data-viewer>

Tagbase-Server: <https://github.com/tagbase/tagbase-server>

ROSETTA: <https://github.com/Unidata/rosetta>

In conclusion Vardis made a few comments on the MESOPP portal. He acknowledged the compliance to data interoperability standards and the searchable portal with comprehensive dataset descriptions. He suggested possible future enhancements:

- A dataset "Level" descriptor (analogous to L0-L4) [this has been proposed also in previous workshop],
- Data access beyond FTP: i.e. use of THREDDS (more adapted than OpenDap for *in situ* data).
- Additional web-visualization capability,
- Use of CF feature class identifiers in data files (DSG types – trajectory/profile).

The following discussion examined the possibilities for continuing the MESOPP effort while extending the approach to a more global coverage. Rudy Kloser (CSIRO, Aus) mentioned that IMOS will continue to be supported by the Australian Government and various partners. Though it can accept acoustic data from other projects, its objective is not to provide facilities for a global database. Andrew Constable, (AAD AUS) who is member of the Executive Committee of the SOOS program (<http://www.soos.aq/>) indicated that SOOS has the goal to become a data hub for the Southern Ocean and would be very likely interested to support the extension of MESOPP CIS to the Southern Ocean, with the possibility to include more international cooperation with the SOOS Country Members.

13. Conclusion of the workshop

This third and last MESOPP workshop was extremely successful to gather participants from multiple research domains, and also Countries. All the objectives and tasks of the project have progressed smoothly despite difficulties inherent to such a large network of collaboration. Promising results and development have been rapidly achieved that now need to be converted to scientific articles and public communications. Invited colleagues are all keen to develop further collaborations and to contribute to an international acoustic database. With other identified potential partners, this represents potentially a huge volume of raw data. Therefore, the problem would be now to select the most useful subsets to be processed according to the standard revised during the project. The most

practical approach could be a transition phase with a project continuing on the tracks of MESOPP for the Southern Ocean but linked to SOOS for its data infrastructure and international framework. One additional working group would be in charge to prepare the extension to the global scale. This group could be supported by the Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR) and would start to collect metadata of existing archived acoustic data in key regions. These conclusions will be further detailed in the roadmap document.

14. References

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15. Appendix

Agenda and list of participants

Mesopelagic Southern Ocean Prey and Predators (MESOPP)

EU H2020-INT-INCO-2015

3rd Workshop

Designing the needs for the implementation of a global coupled acoustic-based observation-modelling system

Falmouth, USA

Coonamesstt Inn, 9-11 Oct 2018

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Meeting Schedule Tuesday 9 October

09:00 Introduction

- Introductory words and MESOPP Highlights
- Adoption of the meeting agenda
- Quick review on project organization (deliverable deadlines, postdocs, budget, amendment)

9:30 Acoustic sampling

- Report of acoustic processing routine and quality checking methods. Acoustic NetCDF standard format (Deliverable D3.1). Provided May 2018. **Sophie Fielding, BAS UK** (01)
- Review of metrics from vessels of opportunity for mesopelagic characterisation. D4.3 To be provided Nov 2018. **Haris Kunnath CSIRO, AUS** (02)

10:15 Extension of the acoustic network of sampling based on opportunities and archives

- The New Zealand acoustic monitoring programme, **Pablo Escobar-Flores, NIWA, NZ** (03)

10:45 Coffee break

11:15 Extension of the acoustic network of sampling (cont.)

- Mesopelagic fish research in the Antarctic Peninsula: Inferences from nets, acoustics and predator diets, **Christian Reiss, NOAA, SWFSC, USA** (04)
- Annual, seasonal and continuous, macro-, meso- and micro-scale observations of the deep scattering layer in the California Current. **Dave Demer, NOAA USA** (05)
- North Atlantic, **Michael Jech, NOAA NEFSC, USA** (06)
- Equatorial Atlantic: The PIRATA network, **Patrick Lehodey, CLS, FR**. (Bernard Bourles, Jereamy Habasque and Arnaud Bertrand, IRD FR and Moacyr Araujo, UFPE, BRA) (07a)
- Subtropical Pacific (New Caledonia), **Patrick Lehodey, FR** (Christophe Menkes, Valerie Alain and Anne Lebourges Daussey IRD) (07b)

13h00: Lunch

14h00: Extension of the acoustic network of sampling (cont.)

- US acoustic archived data, **Chuck Anderson, CIRES, Colorado Boulder, USA** (08)
- EU acoustic archived data and ongoing proposals – the ICES portal **Nils Olav Handegard** (09)

General Discussion

- Other existing projects, archives, people to contact.
- focus on key areas? Key Missing areas?

15h00: Optimal sampling strategy

- Characterizing large scale micronekton assemblages based on acoustic data, in situ sampling and oceanic variables (D4.8 provided June 2018). **Anna Conchon M-O, FR** (10)
- Acoustically-derived global mesopelagic fish biomass. **Roland Proud, UA, UK** (11)
- Atlas of the main mesopelagic fish in the Southern Ocean (D4.6 provided Sep 2018). **Cédric Cotté, Sorbonne University FR** (12)

15h45: tea break

16h00: Working on the Roadmap: integration of the meeting outputs

Roadmap towards a global integrated observing and modelling system (D2.7 to be delivered Nov 2018).

17h00: Final closing

19h00: Meeting Dinner

Meeting Schedule Wednesday 10 October

9h00: Emerging technologies in observation and data processing

- Genomics for species community sampling. **Hilary G. Morrison, Marine Biological Laboratory, USA** (13)
- 30' DEEP-SEE: An instrument platform for sampling the Twilight Zone. **Andone Lavery, WHOI, USA** (14)
- The use of Saildrone for acoustic sampling. **Rudy Kloser** (15)
- PolarPod initiative **Patrick Lehodey** (16)
- Rapidkrill: processing acoustic data onboard Antarctic krill fishing vessels. **Sophie Fielding** (17)

10h45: Coffee break

11h15: Observation models: from acoustic to biomass

- Shedding light on the mesopelagic zone: linking ecosystem models and echosounder observations. **Roland Proud UA UK** (18)
- Potential update on the definition of taxonomic/functional/energetic group in MESOPP models in relation to new acoustic technology information (D3.7 to be delivered Feb 2019). **Rudy Kloser, CSIRO, AUS** (19)
- Acoustic observation model linking ecological models to acoustic signals (D4.2 provided July 2018). **Nils-Olav Handegard IMR, NOR** (20)

Roadmap general discussion

- Progress on the roadmap outline. **Andrew constable AAD, Aus** (21)

13h00: Lunch

14h00: Progress in ecosystem / mid-trophic modeling. 1st validations

- Global estimates with SEAPODYM Anna Conchon, Olivier Titau, P. Lehodey, CLS, FR (22)
- Progress in SEAPODYM-LMTL modeling, Patrick Lehodey, CLS, FR (23a)
- Statistical methods for estimating skill of mesopelagic models to replicate acoustic observations (D4.4 to be delivered Nov 2018). **Anna Conchon M-O, FR** (23b)

- Progress in an ensemble of ecological models in the Indian Sector of the Southern Ocean (size-based, MIZER, Ecopath and Atlantis) **Andrew Constable AAD, AUS** (24)
- Optimal Acoustic Sampling Simulation Experiments, **Anna Conchon M-O, FR.** (25)

15h45: Tea break

16h15: Progress in ecosystem / mid-trophic modeling. 1st validations (Cont.)

General Discussion

- Revising the draft outline of the document.
- Including meeting outputs in the roadmap draft

17h00: close

19h00: Dinner

Meeting Schedule Thursday 11 October

9h00: Mesopelagic prey and predators

- Use of micronekton data and models to improve ecology of top predators (Deliverable D4.9 to be provided Nov-18). **Roland Proud, USTAN, UK** (26)
- Habitats & mesoscale. **Alice Della Penna, Univ. Washington, USA and UBO, FR** (27)
- Modeling the distributions of deep-diving top-level predators, **Jason Roberts, Duke Univ., USA** (28)
- Atlantic bluefin tuna ecology movement, behaviour and micronekton, **Molly Lutacavage, LPRC, USA and Patrick Lehodey CLS, Fr** (29)

11:15 Coffee break

- Identification of physical mechanisms driving pelagic trophic niches of top predators. **Cedric Cotté Univ Sorbonne FR** (30)

12:00: Central Information System for acoustic data and models

- Future of IMOS (CSIRO) **Rudy Kloser** CSIRO
- Future of SONA (BAS) **Sophie Fielding** (BAS)

13h00: Lunch

14h00: Central Information System for acoustic data and models (cont.)

- Access to Oceanographic data. **Vardis Tsonetos, NASA, PODAAC, JPL USA** (31)
- The SOOS program <http://www.soos.ag/> **Andrew Constable, AAD AUS** (32)
- MESOPP catalogue and final release (D2.6 to be delivered Mar 2019) **Patrick Lehodey, CLS, FR**

15h00: General Discussion

- Publications & Communications, News for the web.
- Participation to Conferences; Research papers.
- Progress on the roadmap

15h30 Coffee break

16h00: Working on the Roadmap: integration of the meeting outputs

17h00: Final closing

16. List of Participants

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